

CPC ARTIFICIAL SOLAR LYSIS OF BACTERIAL AND PLASMID DNA IN RAINWATER AND SNOW BY UV, VIS, NIR, TEMPERATURE AND PRESSURE

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Fragmentation required irradiance provided by a 150 W lamp (200-1200 nm)
- *E. coli* was totally inactivated, with DNA fragments < 50 bp (47 min exposure)
- Plasmid DNA was reduced to nicked and linear fragments (17 min exposure and 1-min UVC₂₅₄ pulse)
- These were the lower limits of energy input required for DNA lysis in all replicates
- Mutagenicity rate in irradiated water was <20%, but 35% with 1-min UVC₂₅₄ pulse
- Current mechanistic explanations of fragmentation as bond dissociation factor in ionization, ensuing low-energy electrons, comparable oxidation processes (owing to presence of anions), while the role of vibrations in NIR is still to be researched.

KEYWORDS

Concentrated solar, *E. coli*, pBR322, plasmid, DNA, Ames test, snow, water disinfection

ABSTRACT

Rainwater and snow are natural sources of water with relatively little pollution, so easier to disinfect especially in isolated places. However, rainwater or snow disinfection cannot rely on conventional physicochemical methods that produce toxic disinfection byproducts (DBPs). An alternative using a non-imaging compound parabolic concentrator (CPC) and artificial solar light in the near infrared (NIR), visible (VIS), and ultraviolet (UV) ranges, temperature and pressure, was tested against *Escherichia coli*, its DNA and plasmidic DNA in rainwater and snow. Total organic C, N and anions (via capillary electrophoresis) were measured before disinfection. DNA fragmentation was achieved as shown by gel electrophoresis. After irradiation, AMES tests of mutagenicity probed carryover toxicity resulting from ionization or redox processes. Together, CPC, DNA lysis assessment and carryover toxicity test can be construed as a sustainable water disinfection system.

INTRODUCTION

Rainwater and melted snow for potable use are being adopted worldwide as pressure on water resources increases. Point-of-use rainwater and snow harvesting is usually cheaper than groundwater because of lower infrastructure and pumping costs. Though easier to obtain, precipitation may contain airborne and roof-borne pathogens (Chidamba & Korsten, 2018), requiring disinfection.

E. coli is a thermotolerant, facultative, bacterium often hosted in the human digestive tract, and some strands can be human pathogens. It is an indicator of fecal contamination in the rainwater and snow samples (WHO, 2011). Moreover, bacteria in precipitation and any other water source can quickly develop resistance to antibiotics through plasmids that facilitate transmission of antibiotic resistance genes to other bacteria (Guo et al., 2015), yeast or fungi.

Disinfection using chlorination, iodation, ozonation, Ag, bromine, triclosan and recent antimicrobials, or reverse osmosis do not destroy all organisms and do so selectively (Collivignarelli et al., 2018). Chlorination generates DBPs which are human carcinogens (Prasse et al., 2020) and alternatives to chlorination such as ozone or bromide/iodide compounds still release toxic DBPs (Richardson et al., 2007).

An alternative gaining traction is to disinfect water with concentrated solar power (Madala & Boehm, 2017). Solar energy can be more sustainable to treat high volumes of wastewater (Z. Wang et al., 2015) and reduce process costs (Giannakis et al., 2016). However, solar UVA induce oxidative intracellular damages in bacteria via reactive oxygen species (ROS) (Castro-Alfrez et al., 2016) and UVB interfere with the genetic material of the cell producing mutations that lead to cell death (Strauss et al., 2018).

Also, thermal disinfection appears to be DBP-free (Loo et al., 2012). But boiling alone does not inactivate all bacteria, spores or plasmids, so pressure and UV-VIS-NIR radiation, obtained from artificial light simulating the solar energy spectrum were applied in this study. Together, radiation, temperature and pressure may reduce time and increase efficiency of disinfection. Temperature with pressure has shown to fragment DNA (Islas-Espinoza et al., 2018), but their role in plasmid destruction is still unknown, as current knowledge on plasmids is driven by their usefulness in biotechnology so that interest is rather focused on plasmid preservation.

CPCs are solar concentrating devices, which according to their geometry reach 100-300C; their governing equations can be found in Rincn (2018). Here, the CPCs we built were 2-dimensional, meaning that they have a simple curvature in \mathbb{R}^2 . Around the circular section absorber, the involute describes a parametric curve, which is prolonged by an (anticaustic) parabolic section optimally truncated per Rincn's criterion (Rincn et al., 2009). Fundamental parameters to reach nominal plateau temperature were the absorber's radius (1.2 cm) and the radiation acceptance angle (30). The CPC was covered with a Miro-Sun (Alanod) sheet with total reflection of 95% according to the manufacturer. The plastic parts of the CPC were 3D-printed (MbotGrid II Single) using PLA (Fig. 1).

We addressed the dearth of information on plasmid DNA destruction. We also addressed the assessment of potential toxicity post CPC-disinfection (carryover toxicity).

Fig. 1. Compound Parabolic Concentrator. The 150W artificial lamp delivered 130W (4.5E29 photons/s), including UV. The UVC lamp delivered mean 203 mW/m² UVA and 123 mW/m² UVB through the borosilicate tubes which had widely varying transmittance values (49.5% UVA and 32.7% UVB on average, Appendix Fig. 1). Images ©M. Islas-Espinoza, A. de las Heras.

METHOD

Rainwater and snow samples were harvested in December 2019 from the roof and garden of a building, respectively, at Thompson Rivers University (TRU, Kamloops, BC, Canada). Then, six CPCs with a glass tube absorber, were exposed to pressure and radiation. The tubes contained air, rainwater or snow, and *E. coli* or plasmid. To allow for control and measurement of delivered power, artificial solar radiation was confined between the CPCs and pyramidal bells made of Thermopan® (Fig. 1). Laboratory analyses were performed pre and post radiation. Bacterial and plasmid destruction and toxicity assessments contributed to the safety of the experiment under COVID-19 TRU protocols.

Sample collection and analysis

The rainwater and snow samples (4 L each) were kept at 4°C until analysis. The supernatants were used for the experiments and the sediments discarded. SO₄²⁻, SO₃²⁻, NO₃⁻, NO₂⁻, HCO₃⁻, CH₃COO⁻, Cl⁻ and PO₄³⁻ anions were determined by capillary electrophoresis following Donkor et al. (2015). All anion standards and samples were filtered with 0.45-µm Nylon® syringe filters (Canadian Life Science). All anion determinations were done on a Beckman P/ACE MDQ system (Beckman Coulter Inc, Fullerton, CA, USA) equipped with a UV detector set to 214 nm. Anion separation used a 50 µm internal diameter fused silica capillary (Polymicro Technologies, Phoenix, AZ, USA) with a total length of 60 cm and an effective length of 40 cm. Temperature was maintained at 25°C (± 0.1°C) by means of a liquid fluorocarbon coolant (Beckman Coulter Inc, Fullerton, CA, USA) in the capillary cartridge.

Total organic carbon (TOC) and total nitrogen (TN) in the samples were determined by combustion with a Shimadzu TOC-V (Shimadzu Corporation, Kyoto, Japan), before and following irradiation. TOC, TN, and anion determinations could help understand potentially toxic interactions with radiation.

Bacterial culture before and after irradiation

E. coli DH5 α was cultured in Luria Bertani broth liquid medium containing per L: 10 g tryptone, 10 g NaCl, 5 g yeast extract (Difco, Beckton Dickinson and Co., Sparks, MD, USA), dissolved in distilled water at pH 7, incubated at 37°C overnight and shaken at 250 rpm. The strains were harvested by 10 min centrifugation at 10,000 rpm, washed and suspended in distilled water to achieve an initial optical density (OD) of 1 at 600 nm. Then, 1 mL of bacterial suspension was dosed in each borosilicate tube. After irradiation the tubes were cooled and prepared for plate counts. Three 50 μ L samples were plated in solid agar (tryptone soya with 5% sheep blood, Oxoid) and incubated for 24 h at 37°C to be counted for possible regrowth of the irradiated suspensions.

Plasmid quantification

The plasmid pBR322 (100 μ g, double-stranded closed circle, 4361 bp, molecular weight 2.83×10^6 Da, isolated from *E. coli* (dam⁺, dcm⁺), GeneBank/EMBL accession numbers J01749, K00005, L08654, M10282, M10283, M10286, M10356, M10784, M10785, M10786, M33694, V01119) was diluted in (15 μ g mL⁻¹) distilled water, rainwater or snow. The plasmid concentration was read with a spectrophotometer equipped with a UV-lamp at 260 nm in an agarose gel (1.5%, UltraPure™, Invitrogen) dyed with a gel stain (GelRed™, Nucleic Acid, Biotium, non-carcinogenic unlike ethidium bromide).

Gels for the plasmid and *E. coli* DNA contained an intercalating DNA dye (DirectLoad™, Step ladder, 50-3000 bp, Sigma) along with a sized DNA standard (125-23130 bp, λ Hind III, Sigma). Gels were examined on a transilluminator and photographed with a UV camera. Concentration and yield were determined after gel electrophoresis by comparing the DNA intensity to that of the DNA quantification standards. Aliquots of the plasmid were then transferred to the borosilicate tubes for irradiation.

Artificial solar disinfection

Four treatments were prepared for irradiation (3 replicates): *E. coli* in rainwater, snow or distilled water and plasmid pBR322 in distilled water. These treatments were exposed to artificial sunlight, until temperature plateaued, using lamps (50-100-150W 120V A-21 WH 1SL, Incandescent, 3Way Soft White, 2015 Lumens, 200-1200 nm, Color Temperature 2720 K, Philips DuraMax®). A potentiometer was used to obtain 100 and 150W electricity consumption (The Superior Electric Company, Bristol, Connecticut, USA). For UVC irradiation of plasmids, a UVC lamp (254 nm, Lighting PL-L18W/TUV-18W, germicidal quartz lamp 2G11 4 pin base, 120V, LSE®) was used for 1 min after irradiation with the sunlight lamp. A portable spectrometer (JAZ® Ocean Optics Inc., 1.3 nm spectral resolution attached to a FOV Gershun tube via a flexible optical fiber) showed UVA and UVB in the sunlight lamp so these ranges were measured with Vernier® sensors. Pressure and temperature inside the tubes were measured using (BME280 digital humidity, pressure and temperature sensors, Bosch Sensortec®) sensors whose pins were inserted through small openings in the cap of the tubes. The sensors had to be coated with an epoxy film to protect them. The digital sensors were connected to a SparkFun RedBoard Artemis board to log the data every 1-2 seconds onto a computer. Tube caps and sensors were cleaned with 3% bleach and distilled water using a Q-tip before each treatment to avoid contamination. Data of all experiments are available in Figshare (de las Heras & Islas-Espinoza, 2021).

E. coli spiked in the rainwater and snow was treated according to Islas-Espinoza et al. (2018) in borosilicate glass tubes (Kimax® 45066-25150 KG-33, 50mL, 25x150mm, culture tube, with rubber lined

screw cap, clear, with 88% transmittance at 340 nm) in sample volumes of 10 mL. We measured UVA and UVB irradiance with the Vernier® probes.

Disinfection

Following irradiation, inactivation of bacterial cells and fragmentation of bacterial and plasmidic DNA were determined by colony-culture counting, DNA extraction and inspection of agarose gel electrophoresis UV images. DNA extractions were performed on (1 mL) subsamples using a DNeasy PowerSoil® Kit (Qiagen) following the manufacturer's protocol.

AMES test

AMES tests (Ready to use Assay Kit, Xenometrix®) were performed according to Flückiger-Isler et al. (2004) to evaluate potential mutagenicity of the irradiation and/or potential mutagenic compounds in the rainwater and snow after irradiation. The *Salmonella typhimurium* TA100 strain was used. This strain carries the following mutations: *rfa*, leads to a defective polysaccharide layer that coats the cell surface; therefore, bacteria will be non-pathogenic and more permeable to bulky chemicals; *uvrB*, eliminates the excision repair mechanism, allowing more DNA lesion to be repaired by error-prone DNA repair mechanisms. This strain also contains the *pKM101* plasmid, which enhances chemical and UV-induced mutagenesis via an error-prone recombined DNA repair pathway. The plasmid also confers ampicillin resistance. The positive control mutagenic agents were 2-Nitrofluorene (2-NF) mixed with 4-Nitroquinoline-N-oxide (4-NQO) to revert base-pair substitution mutations. In a (20 mL) Falcon tube containing 5 mL of growth medium (GM) and 5 µL of ampicillin (50 mg mL⁻¹), 5µL of TA100 were added. This tube was incubated overnight at 250 rpm and 37°C. OD was measured at 600 nm and 1 mL of GM was used as a blank; an OD>2 was necessary. The spectrophotometer's cuvette was filled with 900 µL of GM and 100 µL of the bacterial culture (1:10 dilution); therefore, each OD measurement was multiplied by 10. This strain had an OD>2.

A 24-well plate was used to expose *S. typhimurium* post irradiation. In each well, 240 µL of exposed bacteria, 5 µL of mixed 2-NF and 4NQO, 5 µL of rainwater, snow, or distilled water were added (in triplicate); then the plates were incubated at 37°C in a shaker at 250 rpm for 90 min. The AMES tests were carried out on a) negative control: distilled water without mutagen; b) non-irradiated and irradiated samples; c) positive control: the mutagenic mixture of 2-NF and 4NQO.

After incubation, 2.6 mL of indicator medium (IM) were added to each well of the exposure plate, which is a pH indicating medium lacking histidine. Then, each replicate was transferred to a separate 384-well plate using a pipette. 50 µL of exposed cultures mixed with IM were added into every well. The 384-well plates were placed into a sealable plastic bag to prevent evaporation during incubation; they were incubated at 37°C for 2 days.

RESULTS

Disinfection is a DNA fragmentation process

E. coli inactivation was complete: no cell could grow in culture post 100 W artificial solar irradiation. *E. coli* DNA cleavage was so complete at 150 W that no DNA trace was found in gels. However, complete plasmid DNA fragmentation required 150 W plus a 1-min UVC₂₅₄ pulse (Figs. 2 and 3).

The control pBR322 plasmid was closed circular supercoiled double-strand DNA. But following 150W irradiation, DNA fragmentation produced a mixture of fragment forms with supercoiled > linear > nicked gel hydrodynamics, in one of the three replicates; the other two replicates showed only nicked and linear DNA forms and lost the original, supercoiled form (Fig. 2a). After additional 1-min UVC exposure, the supercoiled forms were relaxed, with at least one double strand break, leaving only linear fragments (Fig. 2b). UVC helped nicked forms disappear.

Fig. 2a. Plasmid DNA fragmentation after 150W irradiation (distilled water). The red vertical line denotes a sensor failure in one of the replicates.

Fig. 2b. Plasmid DNA fragmentation after 150W and UVC irradiation (distilled water). The 3-min UVC interval denotes the time to set the UVC lamp to allow for a 1-min pulse. This caused temperature and pressure to decrease. The fastest replicate owed it to absorber preheating.

Fig. 3. *E. coli* disinfection and DNA destruction in rainwater and snow at higher voltage (120V, 150W) irradiance.

Roles of T, P, UV, Vis and NIR

Temperature and pressure in the tubes followed a curve with mean asymptotic values of 52°C, 116 kPa gauge for plasmids at 150 W + UVC and 59°C, 121 kPa gauge for *E. coli* cells. The temperature gain from ambient to the knee of the curve (initial moment of the plateau) took 12-18 min for plasmids in distilled water (2-3°C min⁻¹ gain rate), irrespective of UVC but depending on CPC preheating (Fig. 2b) which took advantage of thermal absorption by CPC materials. Exposure after knee was 18-30 min, and amounted mostly to heat loss. Temperature and pressure gain rates, as well as time to knee were similar for the chemically different rainwater and snow water matrices. However, faster gains, allowed by preheating diminished exposure time while at the same time improving plasmid DNA fragmentation. Energy losses were thermal only, thanks to the CPC bell.

Pressure increase > 1 atm more than compensated for the decrease in boiling temperature at 507 masl TRU Kamloops. Overall, P and T showed a clear mutual relation, so that the liquid was subcooled, the liquid and vapor phases were not present at the same time, while heating took place at near constant volume.

In rainwater and snow water, pressure did not display as marked a plateau, though a knee is noticeable as a change to decreased slope. The differences with distilled water were: phosphate anion in rainwater (PO₄³⁻ ≤50 ppm), chloride anion in snow (Cl⁻ ≤200 ppm) (Appendix Fig. 3). As to TOC and TN contents, they were 0.8539 and 0.2545 mg L⁻¹ in rainwater, respectively and 2.811 and 0.6608 mg L⁻¹ in snow, respectively (Appendix Fig. 4).

Mutagenicity after irradiation

Mutagenicity rates (MR) were best interpreted as probabilities. A 2/3 majority among treatments had mean MR different from zero (Fig. 4); two patterns emerged: snow was consistently different from zero and had wide dispersion around mean MR. More importantly, the presence of *E. coli* tended to raise the mean MR. Both snow (and its chloride ion content) and *E. coli* seemed to interact, with a raised MR second only to UVC. Irradiation did not consistently lead to higher MR. Contrariwise, and most notably, UVC exposure of plasmid in distilled water was the factor of a consistent two-fold increase in mutagenicity probability.

Fig. 4. Mutagenicity in *Salmonella typhimurium* TA100 (spontaneous revertants were subtracted, Appendix Table 1). Negative control is distilled water. Error bars are 2 SE around the mean. Irradiated samples are in bold.

DISCUSSION

Mechanistically, DNA fragmentation corresponds to bond dissociations due to irradiation, with enthalpy $H = U + PV$ where U is the micro (molecular) total internal energy of the DNA and water system (with air and pollutants), with P and V the macro (fluid) pressure and volume. Electromagnetic energy alters U by interacting with electrons and nuclei, increasing translational energy (and temperature hence PV), and vibrational energy. Similarly, the Steffan-Boltzmann law links micro (electromagnetic energy) to macro (fluid temperature) properties and $H = G + TS$ maps the micro Gibbs bond energies to macro (temperature and entropy) properties. Bond dissociation energies remain elusive for polyatomic molecules (Yu-Ran Luo 2009) but single and double strand breaks (SSB and DSB), at more sensitive

bonds emerge from recent mechanistic models of DNA ionization followed low energy electrons (LEEs), dissociative electron attachment (DEA) and vibrational damage, as well as oxidation and reduction.

Aqueous medium

DNA likely remained in the liquid phase and had low probability of wandering into the vapor-saturated atmosphere (except under the push of bubbling) as DNA is 1.7-fold denser than water. H₂O and DNA bind at the negatively charged phosphate nucleoside oxygen (Sanche, 2009), keeping the DNA in the liquid phase. Changes in phosphates are limited by the ionic strength of water, contributing to preserving the DNA (Burmistrova et al., 2013). In addition, higher dissociation energy is needed for DNA in water as water backscatters energy. Also, DNA coils in the physiological medium (Kohanoff et al., 2017), and the hydrated DNA form is usually the B form in which the O atoms in PO₂⁻ bind with the H of H₂O (Guchhait et al., 2016).

UV photolysis

Here, photolysis took place at 4.9-6.2-eV (250-200 nm), which was within the 4.9-6.4 eV (vertical) ionization potential for DNA moieties (Close, 2004). But we were below the 8.5 eV necessary threshold for DNA bases and 12.6 eV for water ionization (Kohanoff et al., 2017). At our low ionization energies, water dissociation energy that released the hydroxyl OH* radical likely dominated over ionization; a major share of our spectral power distribution was in the 1-4 eV (310-1200 nm), in which secondary free electrons yield SSBs (dry conditions) (Nguyen et al., 2011).

Direct ionization creates electron holes. And indirect ionization of solutes and suspended molecules, generates secondary species (electrons and radical cations that contain a hole). Electron holes travel widely between trapping sites, especially in G-rich regions; holes damage the nucleosides and SSB and DSB take place where holes occur (Kohanoff et al., 2017). Direct ionizing and indirect oxidation or reduction also lead to hydrated electrons and H atoms that lead to SSBs and DSBs (Nguyen et al., 2011; Yokoya et al., 2008). SSBs occur more often in the sugar and phosphate nucleosides (Zhang & Tan, 2010) and more often in A or T than G or C bases (Burmistrova et al., 2013). As to oxidation by ROS, it leads to glycosidic C-N bond cleavage (Kohanoff et al., 2017).

Vibrational damage

Initial ionization causes LEEs secondary electrons, followed by DEA, the interaction of LEEs with H₂O molecules whereby a large energy transferred to vibrations causes bond dissociation and trapping (attachment) of electrons to molecules. In DEA, LEEs lead to N-H bond cleavage, C-O bond cleavage between sugar and phosphate, and DEA phosphodiester bond cleavage occurs at lower than ionization (7.5-10 eV) energies (Kohanoff et al., 2017). The G base has two strongly vibrational modes in the IR, C=O and NH₂ (Lee et al., 2006) but with 10⁹ normal modes for *E. coli* DNA (Barth, 2013), research is needed on NIR vibrational modes in *E. coli* and plasmid DNA, and especially the weaker DNA moieties.

Visible light damage

Blue light (BL) damage to DNA is much lower than UV damage, even at 60-fold higher BL irradiances. However, BL is now known to inactivate bacteria, while (520 nm) green light seldom does. *E. coli* is consistently inactivated at 400-405 nm (50-2214 J/cm²) with efficacies better than 99.95%. BL (464 nm) with NIR (850 nm) result in enhanced inactivation, linked to redox changes, increase in superoxide anions and H₂O₂. Efficacy against endospores has also been shown. Uncertainties remain as to BL mechanisms of action: BL excitation of chromophores leading to ROS production still needs rigorous

testing. Regardless, DNA cleavage and oxidation have been shown, as well as membrane damage affecting permeability to ions, attributed to ROS. Other uncertainties include membrane functions, temperature, differences between pulsed and continuous exposures, coherent and non-coherent light, and different exposure times (Y. Wang et al., 2017). As regards plasmids, ROS damage to DNA has been induced by BL in presence of riboflavin (Liang et al., 2013).

Thermolysis and barolysis

Contrary to the abovementioned protective elements of water, the high IR absorbance of water and water vapor traps thermal energy more efficiently than if our test tubes contained dry air. Due to thermal activation, a bond wanders from its equilibrium position. As the bond stretches, its energy increases reaching transition state (energy maximum) past which the bond breaks. Thermal activation influences LEEs-induced strand breaks (Kohanoff et al., 2017).

The effect of pressure is an increase of hydrolysis, especially in cytosine; it may augment modestly however, at a given temperature: hydrolysis doubles between 100 kPa and 200 MPa (Lepper et al., 2018). But increases in dissolved oxygen partial pressure and osmotic pressure might have contributed here to already important oxidative damages caused by indirect ionization and cation reduction processes. Temperature played a role in osmotic pressure per van 't Hoff $\Pi = icRT$.

Without UVC, virtually all the energy was thermal and maximal temperature (86°C) was below the usual melting temperature of 90°C in pure water and 60°C with NaCl (Douki, 2006). It is therefore likely that little melting occurred here. No evidence of this was obtained as *E. coli* fragments were <50 bp and the forms of plasmid fragments pointed to other parameters, more than temperature. The literature is sparse on combined effects of P and T on denaturation, despite the essential role of H bonds in DNA stability. What is known is that hydrogen bond thermal stability is GC > AT: large GC contents dissociate at higher temperature and AT sequences have very low melting points (Burmistrova et al., 2013). Melting might also influence strand breaks as the nucleotides are no longer protected by the backbone.

Redox-induced mutagenicity

A UVC₂₅₄ pulse was required for thorough plasmid disinfection, which otherwise was 66% effective. The 1-mn UVC₂₅₄ pulse led to an almost 2-fold increase in mutation rate in distilled water, compared to different xenobiotic mixtures with anion-induced oxidation potential. UVC₂₅₄ is reckoned to induce mutations. Given current knowledge of ionization-induced DNA damage, LEEs are likely responsible for the increased mutagenicity rate. There are moreover indications that ionization secondary reduction yields twice as many strand breaks than secondary oxidation (Nguyen et al., 2011). An estimate of the duration of mutagenic aftereffects of LEE-induced radicals was 5 days and possibly more. As to anion-induced mutagenicity (with or without radiation exposure), it has been less studied than cation-induced mutagenicity.

Sustainability

The coarse granularity data (P and T of fluids, and gel electrophoresis) obtained on CPC DNA lysis can theoretically be linked to internal (molecular) energy, as discussed above (via enthalpy and the Steffan-Boltzmann law). In practice, proofs of concepts of sustainable DNA lysis still warrant coarse granularity as physical chemistry knowledge of DNA bond dissociations is still constrained to oligomers and bond dissociation energies to diatomic molecule bonds.

CPC lysis sustainable features included energy efficiency and low mutagenicity rates. With the CPC, the lamp total irradiance was used (from the ionizing through the thermal ranges) so that efficiency was increased. The commercially available bell material limited thermal losses. Further sustainability can increase if this setup is PV-powered or better still, a PV-solar CPC hybrid is setup for optimal dispatchability. The results suggested that as temperature and pressure plateaued, additional energy input was lost thermally, meaning that exposure time could be reduced. It is also possible that further reductions in thermal losses could lead to higher temperatures and thence to plasmid DNA lysis higher than 66% so that eventually the 1-mn UVC pulse could be dispensed with, thereby reducing the mutagenicity rate linked to secondary ionizing electrons.

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APPENDIX

Appendix Fig. 1. UVA and UVB transmittance through the borosilicate tubes (emission from the UVC lamp).

Appendix Fig. 2. Gel densitometry. Suggestion of persistent luminescence in the plasmid samples irradiated with UVC needs to be further researched. Said persistence would explain larger bands and intensity, rather than higher DNA concentrations in UVC-exposed plasmids.

Appendix Fig. 4. Total organic carbon and total nitrogen in rainwater and snow.

Appendix Table 1. AMES test samples and results

Replicate	Non-exposed to radiation							Exposed to radiation					Positive control
	Negative control (distilled water)	Snow	Rainwater	Plasmid distilled water	E. coli			Plasmid in distilled water		E. coli			
					Distilled water	Snow	Rainwater	150 W radiation	Plasmid after 150 W + UVC pulse	Control (distilled water)	Snow	Rainwater	
1	6	17	10	6	14	18	11	11	25	14	21	6	48
2	7	14	13	16	16	10	19	19	23	13	19	10	48
3	5	4	4	9	11	9	10	2	22	11	9	9	48